

Transfusion requirements and haematological consequences of Co-inherited glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase deficiency in adults with sickle cell anaemia in north-eastern Nigeria: A cross-sectional study

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Abstract

Background: Co-inheritance of glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase (G6PD) deficiency and sickle cell anaemia (SCA) may produce a complex, double-edged haemolytic state. While SCA causes chronic haemolysis through HbS polymerisation, G6PD deficiency predisposes to acute haemolytic crises triggered by oxidative stress. The haematological profile and transfusion burden of patients harbouring both defects remain incompletely defined. The study aimed to determine the full blood count, reticulocyte count, haemolytic markers, and transfusion history in adult SCA patients with and without G6PD deficiency in Maiduguri, North-Eastern Nigeria. **Materials and methods:** A hospital-based prospective cross-sectional study was conducted over 13 months among 235 HbSS-confirmed SCA patients aged ≥ 18 years in steady state. Quantitative G6PD activity was measured spectrophotometrically (Randox kit). Full blood count, reticulocyte count, and haemolytic indices were determined with an autoanalyser. G6PD activity was categorised as total deficiency (< 2.0 U/g Hb), partial deficiency (2.0–6.9 U/g Hb), or normal (≥ 7.0 U/g Hb). **Results:** Prevalence of G6PD deficiency was 29.3% (3.8% total, 25.5% partial). Mean (\pm SD) G6PD activity was 1.49 ± 0.43 U/g Hb (total), 4.95 ± 1.45 U/g Hb (partial), and 10.39 ± 2.66 U/g Hb (normal). Overall, 79.6% had received a transfusion; the median age at first transfusion was 10 years. Patients with total G6PD deficiency showed significantly higher packed cell volume, haemoglobin, red cell count, and reticulocyte count than those with normal activity ($p = 0.014$, $p = 0.014$, $p = 0.006$, and $p < 0.0001$, respectively). Platelet count was also higher in deficient groups. No significant differences were observed in age at first transfusion or cumulative units transfused across G6PD categories ($p = 0.098$). **Conclusions:** Although G6PD deficiency was prevalent in SCA patients, it was not independently associated with increased transfusion requirements. The elevated red cell indices and reticulocytosis in patients with total deficiency suggest a compensatory marrow response. Routine G6PD screening in SCA remains advisable for individualised care, while larger longitudinal studies are needed to clarify long-term outcomes.

Keywords: G6PD deficiency, sickle cell anaemia, co-inheritance, haematological indices, transfusion

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Introduction

Sickle cell anaemia (SCA) and glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase (G6PD) deficiency are two of the most common inherited erythrocyte disorders in sub-Saharan Africa, the Middle East, and the Indian subcontinent.¹ The overlapping geographical distribution means that co-inheritance is frequent.² SCA is caused by a point mutation in the β -globin gene (Glu \rightarrow Val at position 6), leading to HbS polymerisation under deoxygenation, chronic haemolysis, and vaso-occlusive crises.^{3,4}

Heterozygote advantage against severe malaria has driven the high carrier frequency of 20–25% in West

Africa.^{5,6} The disease is characterised by a pro-oxidant environment due to increased reactive oxygen species and diminished antioxidant capacity.⁷

G6PD deficiency, an X-linked disorder, impairs the pentose phosphate pathway, reducing erythrocytes' ability to withstand oxidative stress.^{8,9} The two most common variants in West Africa are the A-type (G6PD A-) and the Mediterranean type.¹⁰ Acute haemolytic anaemia (AHA) may be triggered by drugs, infections, or fava beans in severely deficient individuals.¹¹ When SCA and G6PD deficiency co-exist, the red cell faces two independent sources of damage. The resulting haematological picture could be additive or synergistic. However, reports on the clinical and laboratory consequences of this double defect are conflicting. Some early studies suggested a beneficial effect on SCA severity,¹² while others found no significant effect on the clinical course.^{13–15} The interaction may depend on residual G6PD activity, coexisting genetic modifiers (e.g., α -thalassaemia, HPFH), and environmental triggers. This study aimed to characterise the steady-state haematological profile, haemolytic markers, and transfusion history in adult SCA patients with varying G6PD activity in Maiduguri, North-Eastern Nigeria, a region with high prevalence of both conditions.

Materials and methods

Study Design and Setting

This hospital-based prospective cross-sectional study was conducted over 13 months (October 2020 – November 2021) at the Haematology and Blood Transfusion Department of the University of Maiduguri Teaching Hospital.

Study Population

Adult patients (≥ 18 years) with confirmed SCA (HbSS by alkaline haemoglobin electrophoresis, pH 8.4–8.6) in steady state were enrolled. Steady state was defined as the absence of painful crises for at least three weeks, no blood transfusion in the preceding three months, and no acute illness.¹⁶ Pregnant women and patients who had received a transfusion within three months were excluded.

Sample Size and Sampling

The minimum sample size was calculated using the formula for a single proportion: $n = Z^2 p(1-p)/d^2$, where $Z = 1.96$ (95% confidence level), $p =$ expected prevalence of G6PD deficiency in SCA (0.27 based on regional data),¹⁷ and $d = 0.05$ (precision). This yielded 213 participants; allowing for 10% incomplete data, 235 were targeted. Consecutive eligible patients attending the clinic were recruited.

Ethical

Ethical approval was obtained from the University of Maiduguri Teaching Hospital Health Research Ethics Committee (UMTH/REC/22/618). Written informed consent was obtained from each participant after individual counselling.

Study Instruments and Laboratory Procedures

Quantitative G6PD assay: G6PD activity was measured in whole-blood lysates using a commercial spectrophotometric kit (Randox Laboratories, UK; Cat. No. PD410) at 340 nm, following WHO recommendations.^{18,19} The principle relies on the reduction of NADP⁺ to NADPH catalysed by G6PD. Erythrocytes were washed three times with normal saline, lysed, and the haemolysate incubated with substrate. Change in absorbance per minute ($\Delta A_{340}/\text{min}$) was converted to activity per gram of haemoglobin (U/g Hb). Reference range: 6.97–20.5 U/g Hb.

Definition of G6PD status:

Participants were categorised as **totally deficient** (activity < 2.0 U/g Hb), **partially deficient** (2.0–6.9 U/g Hb), or **normal** (≥ 7.0 U/g Hb), consistent with WHO classification and the kit's normal range.²⁰

Full blood count (FBC) and reticulocytes: An automated haematology analyser (Sysmex XN-1000; Sysmex Corp., Japan) using impedance and flow cytometry provided complete blood count, red cell indices, and reticulocyte count (absolute and percentage). Reticulocyte index was calculated as reticulocyte count \times (patient's haematocrit / normal haematocrit).²¹
Haemolytic markers: Serum total and unconjugated bilirubin, lactate dehydrogenase (LDH), and haptoglobin were measured using standard clinical chemistry methods.

Transfusion History

A structured questionnaire documented lifetime transfusion status, age at first transfusion, and number of units received in the preceding year and cumulatively. Transfusion frequency was categorised as never, 1, 2, 3, 4, or >4 units per year.

Statistical Analysis

Data were analysed with IBM SPSS Statistics v23.0. Normality was assessed with the Shapiro-Wilk test. Socio-demographic and clinical variables were summarised using means \pm SD or medians (interquartile range) depending on distribution. Groups (total, partial, normal G6PD) were compared with one-way ANOVA or the Kruskal-Wallis test for continuous variables, and chi-square for categorical variables. Post-hoc pairwise comparisons were performed with Bonferroni (ANOVA) or Dunn's test

(Kruskal-Wallis). Transfusion variables (age at first transfusion, total units) were analysed simultaneously with multivariate ANOVA (MANOVA). Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Results

Socio-demographic and Clinical Characteristics
 Of the 235 participants, 107 (45.4%) were male and 128 (54.5%) female. The median age was 22.0 years (IQR 8.0). The majority (87.7%) were single; 54.5% had tertiary education. Nearly 80% had been transfused at least once, with a median age at first transfusion of 10.0 years (IQR 16.0). In the year preceding enrollment, 57.0% received one unit and 20.4% were never transfused. Only 4.7% reported jaundice triggered by drug intake (Table I).

Table I: Clinical Parameters of SCA Patients

Transfusion History	Frequency	Percentage
Age at First transfusion (years)	10.00(16.00) ^a	
Never transfused	48	20.4
0-1 years	9	3.8
1-5 years	30	12.8
5-10 years	41	17.5
10-15 years	44	18.7
15-20 years	39	16.6
>20 years	24	10.2
Total	235	100
Frequency of Transfusion	48	
Never transfused		20.4
1 per year	134	57
2 per year	12	5.1
3 per year	22	9.4
4 per year	11	4.7
>4 per year	8	3.4
Total	235	100
History of jaundice with drug intake		
Yes	11	4.7
No	224	95.3
Total	235	100

^aMedian (Interquartile Range)

G6PD Status and Haematological Parameters

Patients with total G6PD deficiency had significantly higher mean packed cell volume (PCV), haemoglobin (Hb), and red blood cell (RBC) count than those with normal activity ($p = 0.014$, $p = 0.014$, $p = 0.006$, respectively; post-hoc, total vs. normal). The partially deficient group showed intermediate values, not statistically different from normal (Table III). Reticulocyte percentage, absolute count, and reticulocyte index were significantly higher in totally and partially deficient groups compared to normal ($p < 0.0001$, $p < 0.001$). White blood cell count did not differ across groups, while platelet count was higher in G6PD-deficient

G6PD Activity and Deficiency Categories

Prevalence of G6PD deficiency was 29.3%: 9 patients (3.8%) had total deficiency, 60 (25.5%) partial deficiency, and 166 (70.6%) normal activity. Mean G6PD activity in the three groups differed significantly (one-way ANOVA, $F[2,232] = 589.3$, $p < 0.0001$), with all pairwise comparisons being significant ($p < 0.0001$) (Table II). Due to the small number of totally deficient individuals ($n = 9$) and the X-linked nature of G6PD, separate gender-based analyses were not feasible; however, 7 of the 9 totally deficient patients were male.

Table II: Comparison of G6PD enzyme activity at different levels among SCA

G6PD	SCA	
	Mean \pm SD	Estimated Mean
Totally deficient ^a	1.49 \pm 0.43	1.552
Partially deficient ^b	4.95 \pm 1.45	4.941
Normal ^c	10.39 \pm 2.66	9.696

Factorial ANOVA (Two-way ANOVA)

Multiple Comparison

G6PD: a & b = P

< 0.0001 , **a & c = P**

< 0.0001 , **b & c = P**

< 0.0001 ,

Interaction: Normal

(**a & b = P** < 0.0001).

The key haematological finding was that totally G6PD-deficient SCA patients had higher PCV, Hb, and RBC counts, accompanied by marked reticulocytosis. At first glance, this appears paradoxical: one expects that adding an oxidative haemolytic defect to SCA would lower red cell mass. Several explanations are possible. First, the higher reticulocyte count may itself compensate for haemolysis, maintaining a younger and larger red cell population that is more resistant to sickling.

patients (Kruskal-Wallis $p = 0.031$). No significant differences were observed in total bilirubin, unconjugated bilirubin, LDH, or haptoglobin (Table III).

Transfusion Requirements and G6PD Status

Mean age at first transfusion was 4.89 ± 3.96 years (total deficiency), 12.60 ± 2.17 years (partial), and 10.73 ± 2.27 years (normal). Cumulative units transfused were similar across groups (5.28 ± 4.16 , 5.36 ± 2.43 , and 5.73 ± 2.76 , respectively). MANOVA showed no statistically significant overall effect of G6PD status on transfusion variables (Wilks' $\Lambda = 0.956$, $F[4,462] = 1.977$, $p = 0.098$) (Table IV).

Table III: Comparison of G6PD deficiency, Full Blood Count and Haemolytic markers in SCA

SCA	Totally Deficient ^a (9)	Partially Deficient ^b (60)	Normal ^c (166)	F(df)	P-value ^a
	Mean ±SD	Mean ±SD	Mean ±SD		
PCV (%)	24.04 ±7.60	19.60 ±5.91	18.64 ±5.34	4.343(2,232)	0.014
Hb(mg/dl)	8.19 ±2.27	6.70 ±1.89	6.39 ±1.83	4.328(2,232)	0.014
RBC X10 ⁹	2.99 ±0.94	2.39 ±0.83	2.22 ±0.72	5.223(2,232)	0.006
WBC X10 ⁹	9.76(9.49)	11.86(3.88)	13.09(5.87)	4.876(2)	0.087 ^A
Platelet	309.00(75.00)	399.00(196.00)	360.00(161.00)	6.935(2)	0.031 ^A
Reticulocytes (%)	8.60(4.15)	8.50(2.55)	7.50(1.90)	24.873(2)	<0.0001 ^A
Retics Count	277.20(138.69)	183.77(124.67)	152.74(84.06)	21.435(2)	<0.0001 ^A
Retics Index	5.11(2.69)	3.98(2.53)	3.53(1.71)	18.89(2)	<0.0001 ^A
LDH1	160.90 ±76.49	156.55 ±61.95	153.44 ±62.80	0.101(2,232)	0.904
Total Bilirubin	41.70(35.20)	38.20(34.10)	36.1(32.2)	2.232(2)	0.328 ^A
Unconjugated Bilirubin	24.48(26.90)	22.05(31.10)	18.80(19.4)	3.955(2)	0.138 ^A
Haptoglobin	56.45(15.55)	58.04(12.16)	61.60(30.78)	1.191(2)	0.551 ^A

^aOne-Way ANOVA, ^AKruskal-Wallis H test, Median (Interquartile range)

Multiple comparisons:

PCV: (a & c = *P* 0.014), Hb: (a & c = *P* 0.014), RBC: (a & c = *P* 0.008), Platelet: a & b = *P* 0.049,

Retics %: c & a = *P* <0.0001, c & b = *P* 0.038), Retics Count: (c & a = *P* 0.003, c & b = *P* 0.001), Retics Index: (a & c = *P* 0.009, b & c = *P* 0.002),

Table IV: Comparison of transfusion requirements and G6PD deficiency in SCA

	Totally deficient	Partially deficient	Normal	F(value)	P- value
	Mean ±SD	Mean ±SD	Mean ±SD		
Age at first transfusion	4.89 ±3.96	12.60 ±2.17	10.73 ±2.27	1.977(0.956)	0.098 ^a
Total units	5.28 ±4.16	5.36 ±2.43	5.73 ±2.76		

^aMANOVA (Wilks' Lambda), Box's Test *p* = 0.159,

Discussion

This study found a G6PD deficiency prevalence of 29.3% among adult SCA patients in Maiduguri, consistent with figures from Saudi Arabia (27.5%)²² and Burkina Faso (27.0%),²³ but lower than reports from Ghana (35.8%).²⁴ Such variation reflects differences in local allele frequencies, assay methods, and study populations. Our data confirm that G6PD deficiency is common in Nigerian SCA cohorts and supports calls for routine screening.¹ Second, G6PD deficiency might reduce oxidative stress-induced membrane damage that otherwise accelerates haemolysis in SCA, a hypothesis advanced decades ago.¹² Third, measured G6PD activity in whole-blood lysates is confounded by reticulocytosis—young red cells have higher enzyme activity, potentially misclassifying truly deficient individuals as partial or normal.²⁵ This inflation could explain why the “normal” group had lower RBC indices: they may include patients with true G6PD deficiency masked by reticulocytosis, whose marrow response is less robust. This limitation, shared with most studies not using reticulocyte-adjusted activity or genotyping, must temper interpretation.

We observed no significant difference in transfusion requirements by G6PD status. Although totally deficient patients received their first transfusion at a younger age (4.9 years vs. 10.7 years), the overall multivariate test was non-significant, and the study lacked power to detect a modest effect given only 9 totally deficient participants. Other cross-sectional studies have similarly reported no association between G6PD deficiency and transfusion frequency.^{24,26} Prospective studies that capture transfusion-triggering events are needed. Markers of haemolysis (bilirubin, LDH, haptoglobin) were not significantly different between groups. This may reflect the steady-state condition of enrolment; G6PD-related haemolysis is typically episodic. The lack of a significant gradient in LDH, despite higher reticulocytosis, might indicate that the increased red cell turnover is balanced by a more efficient clearance or a younger cell population less prone to intravascular destruction.

The study has inherent limitations. The cross-sectional design precludes causal inference.

Only 9 patients had total deficiency, limiting statistical power and the generalisability of comparisons involving this subgroup. G6PD activity was not corrected for reticulocyte count, and variant typing was not performed; heterozygous females with skewed X-inactivation could be misclassified. We did not examine peripheral blood films, nor measure iron status or inflammatory markers that influence haemoglobin. Participants were adults who had survived childhood, introducing a potential survivorship bias. Finally, the single-centre setting may not represent all Nigerian SCA populations.

Conclusions

G6PD deficiency affected nearly one-third of adult SCA patients in this North-Eastern Nigerian cohort, but co-inheritance was not independently associated with increased transfusion burden. The unexpected finding of higher red cell indices and reticulocytosis in severely deficient patients warrants further investigation using reticulocyte-adjusted G6PD assays or molecular genotyping. Routine G6PD screening in SCA clinics is recommended to identify individuals at risk of oxidative haemolysis, enabling tailored counselling and avoidance of known triggers. Multicentre, longitudinal studies are required to delineate the long-term haematological and clinical impact of this common genetic interaction.

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Competing interests

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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